

IElectrix project – Demand Response

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Abstract

IElectrix is a response to the Horizon 2020 Call of the European Commission: “Integrated local energy systems”.

Within a cooperation agreement signed by 4 European partners and TATA POWER Delhi Distribution Limited (TPDDL), Shakti demonstration is set up in Delhi to explore innovative solutions allowing the implementation of “Local Energy Communities” using local photovoltaic (PV) and storage for self-consumption approach.

In 2013, TPDDL launched its first automated Demand Response (DR) pilot program that allowed direct load control across 165 commercial and industrial consumers. The program successfully demonstrated direct load control DR that provided in peak load reduction.

By 2020, with Advanced Metering Infrastructure (AMI), TPDDL is looking to broaden DR program by extending behavioral DR (BDR) program across its residential consumers. BDR hinges on consumer participation as loads will be managed entirely by them in response to critical peak pricing. With smart phones acting as the gateway to home automation solutions, use of smart plugs to control home appliances such as air conditioners and other high-power equipment can be considered to allow functions such as “set it and forget it” mode for consumers. These DR initiatives are aligned with IElectrix objectives, and some of them will be carried out in the framework of such project.

The paper will provide insights into various DR programs planned, associated challenges that promises a value proposition to all participants and helps establish that consumer engagement is the most critical component for a successful adoption of DR program in this initiative across TPDDL.

Keywords

Advanced Metering Infrastructure, Demand Response, Local Energy Communities, Critical Peak Rebates, Critical Peak Pricing

I. INTRODUCTION

The Shakti demonstration in Delhi aims at showing how innovative solutions allow the implementation of Local Energy Communities (LEC) using local PV units and the self-consumption approach.

Low Voltage (LV) networks, considered uncritical, have been disregarded for the last 60 years. As a result, their

characteristics, their status in terms of voltage plan and load level are poorly known. Furthermore, in most of the cases, no remote-controlled devices are available in this part of the grid neither for grid configuration nor for load management.

Consequently, its management requires new investments to monitor and control voltage and congestion aspects, especially in scenarios of PV insertion.

Two kinds of solutions will be implemented within Shakti demonstration:

- One solution uses dedicated assets like on load tap changers on distribution transformers, storage capabilities allowing large PV insertion and islanding operation during outages.
- The other solution uses DR at customer premises level combined with a grid state estimation based on data coming from currently deployed smart meters and from real-time. In this pilot, real-time data is fed by Remote Terminal Units (RTU) directly. In normal operation, the real-time data would come from the ADMS being fed by the RTU.

While time-varying demand response program is lucrative from a low CAPEX standpoint, it has its share of challenges to be tackled. This paper will present more in detail the DR solutions implemented TPDDL and then more precisely in the Shakti demonstration site.

II. DEMAND RESPONSE IN TPDDL

A. Why Demand Response?

Fig. 1. Load duration curve of normalized capacity vs. hours per year

Fig. 1 above shows the load duration curve that is useful in understanding the quantity of DR programs that can be deployed. Load duration curves are determined by ordering the load in all hours from highest to lowest and plotting the load in that descending order to help identify the maximum load received during one hour, two hours or top % of hours to address using cost competitive measures.

The character of the system load will determine the extent of DR measure that will be most cost effective in meeting load growth and deferring investment in either additional system capacity or additional generation.

With an annual load factor of 60% which however increases in summer months, peaking at 81% in September. For example, if reducing load in only 10 hours can reduce peak load by 5% then DR may be a more cost-effective solution than a new power plant contract at meeting load in these hours. These peak 10-30 hours present opportunities for capacity investment deferral that can come from a DR program: incentivized consumers can shift net load from peak to off peak hours to offset cost such as new generator or distribution CAPEX.

On a global scale, it is estimated that the global market for demand response enabling technologies could grow to \$9.7 billion by 2023 [1]. This surely justifies why TPDDL and other Distribution System Operators (DSO) should be more and more involved in developing DR programs.

B. Demand Response Scheme in TPDDL

At TPDDL, a time varying demand response mechanism is commonly used. It relies on consumer participation, choice and behaviour to modulate their loads. It rewards the required changes by incentivizing load reduction or pay premium for usage.

There are two ways to consider time varying DR:

1. Critical Peak Rebates (CPR)

With a critical peak rebate program, the peak demand periods or emergency events anticipated by the utility are relayed to their customers, and the provision of load curtailments by customers during those periods are remunerated pro rata at a predefined rate offered by the utility.

2. Critical Peak Pricing (CPP)

Critical peak pricing is a tariff that adds a time-dependent rate to the normal rate (or Time of Use (ToU) rate) based on day-ahead demand forecasts so that the energy prices are sufficiently high during actual peak demand hours to induce reduced consumption. The number of days in which CPP rates are applied is usually limited, and the activation of these rates can range from one day ahead to a few minutes prior to the peak load event.

Note: The key differentiation is that ToU tariffs are calculated and communicated well ahead of time; and CPP and CPR only require communication during critical peak hours. The success of these mechanisms hinges on real-time communication that can be satisfied over SMS, text, emails.

At TPDDL, DR programs that are variants of either CPP or CPR are developed but may hold a different preference for each consumer and might help them choose one program as opposed to none! For example, Time of Day (TOD) tariff is one type of DR but does not offer real visibility into the actual cost of supply or incentivize the consumer in anyway. It simply is seen as an extension of tariff. Such a program is also referred to as BDR and a defined incentive with varying prices can help reduce peak demand by either shedding load or shifting demand to non-peak hours.

In the short run, flattening of peak demand can significantly reduce expensive spot energy purchases, reduce penalties due to unscheduled interchanges and prevent unplanned load shed due to imbalance of demand and supply.

In the long run, a well-defined program can provide steady peak demand reduction through DR and help offset network capital expenditure - both from generation capacity standpoint and in distribution upgrades. Demand response is also becoming an important balancing resource, with increasing shares of variable distributed renewable generation sources. In Delhi that is landlocked with extensive dependency on coal as it is the dominant source unlike wind and hydro in other parts of the country, solar PV is the main source of renewable energy.

III. FOCUS ON THE DEMAND RESPONSE PROGRAM IN THE SHAKTI DEMONSTRATOR – IELECTRIX PROJECT

A. Size & Context of the Demonstrator

A DR program is also being developed within the IElectrix project, this time involving not only TPDDL but also partners like Enedis, Geco Global, Schneider Electric and Odit-e.

Given the significance of this program, the immediate next step was to understand the consumer load profile to estimate the available DR potential. For this pilot, we have considered the consumers connected to the Shakti MV/LV substation with their load shapes to cluster them in different categories. For this pilot, a total of 38 consumers were considered and the following Table 1 provides their clustering and relevant details.

TABLE 1: CLUSTERING AND RELEVANT DETAILS OF THE 38 CUSTOMERS

Connection Type	Government	Private	Solar Capacity	Grand Total
Street Light and Traffic Signal	3			3
Commercial (School/ College/ Dorm)		9	194 Kw	9
Commercial (Govt Establishment)	1			1
Residential	2	23	4 kW	25
Grand Total	6	32	198 kW	38

B. Methodology

To estimate the DR potential, this particular pilot assumes response rate as well as the participation rate to be a 100% given the small size of the consumers.

$$\text{DR potential} = \text{Aggregate consumer peak demand} \\ * \text{DR as a \% of peak load}$$

In real scenario, a time varying BDR program is preferred due to less infrastructure-intensive program as opposed to direct load control DR. BDR does not necessarily provide a firm load reduction and may also present a low response rate therefore, unlike ADR, BDR program success directly hinges on the quantum of enrolment.

While the peak demand estimates might not vary significantly if measured over the year, the load factors do vary significantly as consumers in Delhi experience high peak loads during summer months which start as early as April till September, thus affecting the estimates of the aggregate peak load for each customer category. Given that the pilot program was in its initial stage of deployment, the estimates are likely to be improved as data on more DR events and additional consumers are measured over a longer period of time.

C. Operation of the DR Program in Shakti

In Shakti, DR program will be used, among other use cases, to mitigate forecasted congestions on the LV network, the BDR program will be activated when the operation of the MV/LV substation is not expected to meet the requirements. To do so, algorithms are developed to digitize the grid and use this “digital twin” to predict how it will behave the next day. The process of such algorithm is depicted in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. Grid digitization process

Hereafter is a sequence of operations that show how the Demand Response program runs in the Shakti pilot:

1. Odit-e generates and transfers to TPDDL a schedule file with customer identification and required level of power reduction for the next 24 hours.
2. TPDDL, through a dedicated system, informs the relevant customer of the required power reduction to meet proper operation condition.
3. Customer, through the specific communication and engagement activities (see D) is solicited to act and to limit its consumption.
4. TPDDL collects and transfers updated customers' load curves to Odit-e.
5. Odit-e integrates customer engagement in the model to optimize DR program effectiveness.

D. Customer Engagement & Benefits

Dynamic tariff involves substantially increased retail prices during times of heightened consumption (for example on abnormally cold winter days) or when the stability of the system is threatened, and blackouts may occur. These schemes represent an attempt to nudge consumers to account for the cost of producing/transporting electricity and network constraints in their consumption behaviour.

Insights from social sciences [2][3][4], and meta-analyses of dynamic tariff pilots [5][6][7], all point to four important considerations for the Shakti DR demonstration:

1. The prospect of financial savings in and of themselves is often not motivating enough, particularly in CPP/CPR programs where critical events are seldom and short in duration.
2. At the start of the pilot, most people have only a vague idea of how much energy they are using for different purposes and what sort of difference they could make by changing day-to-day behaviour.
3. Energy consumption feedback is an essential element in effective learning and behaviour change, as well as in raising social awareness, changing consumers' attitudes, and leading them to engage critically with their habits and practices.
4. As a result, pilots combining dynamic pricing with consumption feedback and tailored awareness and education activities are more effective at reaching their objectives.

Geco Global and TPDDL will implement a range of communication and consumer engagement activities that consider the specificities of the territory and the people living in it.

The starting point will consist in understanding the community and its members. Design personas will be specified so that differences in attitudes, perceptions, emotions, ability to make changes and behaviours around dynamic pricing and the energy transition in general are fully assessed.

This important dimension provides a lever to engage with consumers' values and attitudes in relation to topics such as environmental concern, desire to save money, desire to engage in a community project, and interest in novel technology during the ensuing communication and awareness campaigns of the pilot activities and positive local impacts through tailored (i.e., based on personas specified) messages and channels.

In addition to this deeper consumer understanding, the existing knowledge and interest gaps will also be taken into consideration. Perhaps because most consumers are not fully aware of their own energy consumption, increase in knowledge and concern from mass communication campaigns may not translate into observable change of behaviour unless the general information is combined with other more tailored and targeted techniques. In addition, dynamic prices themselves do not generate peak clipping; they generate the nudge that in turn may lead to peak time savings. It is therefore paramount to address pilot participants' expressed concerns and provide them with tips and advice on how to take advantage of the smart plugs and dynamic tariffs as well as with quick feedback on the impact of their actions during the critical peak thereby enabling them to directly identify links between activities and consumption. State-of-the-art content and interaction design techniques will be used to ensure tips and advice are relevant (i.e., personalised and based on user needs and capabilities), timely (i.e., soon before and during an event), easily accessible and written in a way that is easy to understand (i.e., using clear and non-expert language).

Since we are not our customers, an evaluation framework and a set of metrics will be designed allowing for the continuous tracking and calibration of the engagement activities (e.g., consumer satisfaction, impact of communication campaigns) therefore ensuring consumer feedback are considered and appropriate adjustment measures can be taken.

The benefits of the DR program for a participating customer include financial incentives for participating in the DR program, and also the savings that result due to reduced energy consumption during peak hours. With CPP and CPR programs where the rates are defined for those hours are significantly higher than TOD, consumers are likely to save by shifting their consumption from peak hours to non-peak hours.

DR incentives should be greater than the opportunity cost available to consumers as well as provide savings to make it lucrative for the consumers to enrol and participate. For a utility, the cost share revolves around primarily the administrative cost of the program, fixed cost of infrastructure and revenue loss if it leads to load shed vs load shift.

E. Expected Results

CPP program will be carried out from March 2021 all through till 2024 and onwards amongst 38 consumers. In its pilot, the CPR program is expected to bring an average load reduction between 20% – 30% during emergency events, with consumers incentivized between INR 45-INR 55 per hour per day during these events. Unlike the ADR program run earlier in 2013, the program had primarily 165 Industrial and some commercial consumers who contributed to an average load reduction of 8MW and required extensive capex to execute

that program. That pilot study involved 144 customers with a total coincident peak load of about 25 MW responding to a total of 17 events. By building type, the 75th percentile of responses ranged from 3% in educational buildings to 62% in pumping facilities, with an overall 75th percentile of responses at 10% of total load [8]. Honeywell estimates that if similar projects were deployed in the commercial and industrial sectors across all of India, the projects could potentially decrease the country's peak electricity demand by around 7.5 GW, or 5% of total peak demand [9].

Fast forward to 2021, TPDDL is extending and expanding DR program by bringing time varying DR program to all include residential/domestic customers, with the potential to scale up to over two hundred thousand consumers by 2025.

IV. CONCLUSION

Currently, time-varying demand response mechanism is not widely used in India. Only time-of-day tariffs are offered to large commercial and industrial customers in some states. Otherwise, electricity is typically supplied at a predetermined tiered tariff structure, with subsidies for agricultural and residential customer classes that often result in financial losses for the distribution utilities [10].

Demand response may be able to mitigate these financial pressures by reducing the per-unit cost of electricity, especially if the demand response is incented from the subsidized sectors.

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